

On the Space/Time Correlation of mmWave AoAs: Concept and Experimental Validation

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Abstract—The Sub-6GHz multi-path channel model suggests that the angle of arrivals (AoAs) and angle of departures (AoDs) of dominant rays follow a uniform distribution. Moreover, AoA/AoD varies interdependently from one coherence time/space to another. Several of the recent works on millimeter wave (mmWave) transmissions suggest otherwise, where some presume that it is possible to predict the AoAs/AoDs from nearby users (correlation over space) while others presume that beamforming coherence distance/time is higher than the channel coherence distance/time. The results in existing works, however, are often based on abstract models (two rays model), simulation results (typically rays tracing simulator), and, in many cases, the presence of a Line-of-Sight (LoS) link. In an effort to support or refute such a conjecture, we have carried out a real-world experiment in indoor office environments with high Non-LoS (NLoS) probability. We use statistical Bayesian learning to infer a statistical model on AoAs and extract insightful information.

Index Terms—Angle-of-arrival, space/time correlation, mmWave, statistical learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Sub-6GHz transmissions typically exhibit the features of rich-scattering channels that can be modeled by the Rayleigh fading. The model suggests that AoAs/AoDs of dominant rays vary independently at every other channel coherence time (the time required by a mobile user to cross a distance in the order of half-wave, i.e., coherence distance.) Accordingly, the AoAs of two nearby users that are distance apart by more than the coherence distance experience uncorrelated AoAs¹.

The sensitivity of mmWave transmissions to blockage results in a sparse channel structure, where a few numbers of scattered rays reach the receiver. Such an observation has been interpreted in two different ways. Some have believed that there are few rays within each channel coherence distance/time, but their AoAs/AoDs may vary independently at every other channel coherence distance/time [1]–[3]. It implies that the transmitter/receiver has to adjust the beam-steering direction at every other channel coherence time that is in the order of microseconds. It is to highlight that the mmWave transmissions are characterized by short coherence time. For instance, the channel coherence time decreases by a factor

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¹Given to reciprocity of the channel, the same results apply for the AoDs. In the rest of the paper, we focus on the AoAs and the same results apply to the AoDs given the aforementioned uplink-downlink channel duality.

of more than thirty when shifting from the 1 GHz carrier frequency to the 30 GHz one. Meanwhile, others stand for the fact that there are few rays within each channel coherence distance/time, and their AoAs/AoDs remain correlated beyond the channel coherence distance/time [4]–[6]. The latter conjecture can be intuitively validated in the presence of LoS, two rays model, and static environment (absence of moving obstacles) [7]. However, it is hard to confirm in a dynamic environment with a high probability of NLoS.

In [1]–[3], the authors consider that the AoAs/AoDs of spatially sparse rays may vary independently from one coherence time to another. Meanwhile, they exploited the sparse structure of the mmWave channel to reduce the computational complexity to estimate the beam-forming matrix for multi-input multi-output systems.

If the correlation among AoAs and AoDs across channel coherence space/time does indeed exist, it can provide several advantages, including accelerated beam search times, extended beam alignment beyond channel coherence time, and predictive capabilities for phase shifter configurations. Initiatives have been made in [8], in which the authors introduce the concept of beam coherence time. The latter refers to the time over which the beam direction, and implicitly, the AoAs of dominant rays, remains almost time-invariant. The authors considered mmWave transmissions in the presence of a strong LoS link and proved theoretically that mmWave beam coherence time is longer than the channel coherence time. In [9], the proposed beam inference techniques exploit the correlation among the dominant rays’ AoAs (reciprocally AoDs) of a given user and the users in its proximity (typically located in a distance higher than coherence distance). Thus, the efficiency of the proposed approach heavily relies on the underlying assumption of high correlation/similarity among the AoAs of users in the same vicinity. Several other works assume a correlation between the location of the users and the AoAs of dominant rays [4], [5]. The authors proposed machine learning-based techniques that exploit an estimate of the user location to predict the AoAs of dominant rays. The essence of the proposed approaches is to collect data offline on AoAs at different locations and then match online the instantaneous position of a user with one of the learned beam setups. Thus, there is an underlying assumption regarding a correlation between AoAs over time (duration between the data collection and the instantaneous AoAs prediction) and space (distance between the instantaneous user location and

the matching data point). In [6], the authors suggest scanning the candidate beams according to the descending order of the utilization frequency of AoAs. The gain in the beam search time relies heavily on the assumption that the AoAs of dominant rays are more probable from certain directions than others. In particular, they assumed that the AoAs follow a wrapped normal distribution.

On the other hand, a recent experiment conducted in an indoor office environment over the 28GHz band showed that the two rays model falls short of representing the mmWave channel, and rather, a five rays model is deemed to be a better fit for the measurements [10]. While the authors did not provide results pertaining to the correlation of AoAs, utilizing the five-ray model could potentially introduce added uncertainty regarding the existence of AoAs correlation, particularly in the context of NLoS links. The results may contradict with the investigations in [4], [5] that are often based on channel simulator (e.g., Wireless Insite), abstract models (two rays model), the presence of LoS, absence of moving obstacles (dynamic environment), to name a few. Hence, the conjecture concerning the correlation among AoAs beyond the channel coherence distance/time remains unverified and necessitates real-world experiments to establish its existence and investigate associated statistical attributes, like probability and coherence distance.

In an effort to clarify the correlation between AoAs, we conducted an experiment in a high NLoS indoor office environment. It consists of placing a 28 GHz transmitter at one end of the corridor (hallway) and moving a horn antenna receiver at different offices and different locations in the same office. The receiver was placed randomly in each of the offices. The receiver, mounted on a rotating platform, can precisely measure the power of received signals from all angles (360° degrees) with one-degree accuracy. The experiment was conducted in a real-world setting during working hours, in the presence of humans and various obstacles, such as experimental equipment and furniture (more details on the used equipment and experiment parameters are provided in Sec. II-A.) We use Bayesian statistical learning to classify the measurements in an unsupervised fashion and infer statistics on the AoAs (see Sec. III) [11]–[19]. In section IV, we provide the experimental results on the probability distribution of the AoAs of dominant rays, and statistics on the AoAs coherence distance. Conclusions are drawn in Sec. V.

II. EXPERIMENT SETUP AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

A. Experiment setup

The measurements were carried out in a dynamic environment during working hours, encompassing a 110m long, 1.8m wide corridor bordered by offices and laboratories with diverse dimensions, all characterized by a high likelihood of NLoS conditions. Within this context, obstacles, comprising moving humans and furniture/equipment, displayed notable disparities in their occurrence, placement, and size from one laboratory or office to another. The transmitter was positioned at one end of the hallway, while the receiver was placed at various positions,

Fig. 1: Experiment environment.

encompassing different offices/laboratories, locations within them, and positions within the hallway. Measurements were also collected around the hallway intersection corners. Fig.1 illustrates the measurement environment, showcasing representative obstacles. The spacing between successive measurement points was approximately 1 foot (30cm).

We use a narrowband sounder, transmitting a 28 GHz continuous-wave (CW) tone at 22 dBm into a 10 dBi horn with 55° half-power beamwidth in both elevation and azimuth. The receiver has a 10° (24 dBi) horn mounted on a rotating platform, allowing a full angular scan every 400 ms with 1° azimuthal angle sampling. The receiver records power samples at a rate of 740 samples/sec, with a 20 kHz receive bandwidth and effective noise figure of 5 dB. The system was calibrated to assure absolute power accuracy of 0.15 dBm. The sounder’s high dynamic range allows reliable path loss measurements up to 171 dB with directional antenna gains. Although the proposed framework is not specific to a given propagation environment, the numerical results provided in this section pertain to the indoor office environment.

We collected measurements from around 700 different locations. At each location (measurement point), we collected measurements for 10 seconds where the sounder rotates with a speed of 150 rounds per minute, i.e., 2.5 rounds per second. As the received power is collected for each 1° azimuthal angular, we obtained measurements with an approximate size of $2.5 \times 10 \times 360 \times 700 = 9000 \times 700$. The receiver records both the received power and their associated azimuthal angles, with our reference direction being geodetic north (true north).

B. Preliminary results

Figures 2a and 2b depict samples of AoAs collected from two separate offices, highlighting a partial similarity in the radiation patterns (AoAs corresponding to dominant rays). This suggests a correlation among AoAs extending beyond the channel coherence distance/time. Notably, these dominant signal directions exhibit a connection with the physical orientation of office doors, which aligns with the expectations given the limited penetration of mmWave signals. However, it is intriguing to observe cases where measurements within the same office, as exemplified in Figs. 2b and 2c (with a separation of approximately one meter between measurement points),

Fig. 2: Samples of azimuthal radiation patterns inside offices.

reveal entirely dissimilar AoAs' profiles. This observation prompts the conclusion that while there may exist a probable correlation among AoAs of dominant rays beyond the channel coherence distance (typically in the order of millimeters), it is not guaranteed with high certainty. Therefore, further investigation is needed to quantify this correlation's likelihood across space and identify potential patterns.

III. AOAS STATISTICS INFERENCE

The objective of this study is to derive probabilistic models on the AoAs, including, the probability distribution function (PDF) of AoAs and the probability of AoAs correlation as a function of the crossed distance. Contrary to the work in [6] in which the authors anticipated that the AoAs follow an unimodal distribution (wrapped normal distribution), the collected data showed that it may not be the case and mixture of distributions (multimodal) better fit the measurements. Since the order (number of modes) of the mixture may not be known a priori, we opt for the nonparametric (unknown order) option of the Bayesian statistical learning approach. Firstly, we provide a brief overview of the fundamental principles of machine learning utilized in this study. Secondly, we establish the features and output of our chosen learning approach.

A. Bayesian Learning

In Bayesian statistics, we express any form of uncertainty as randomness. Therefore, we represent the distribution parameters (means, variances, and mixture weights) as set of random variables, denoted by $\Theta = \theta_i, i \in \mathbb{N}$, which take values in the space Ω . This implies that the model's parameters to be inferred are treated as random variables. Consequently, the observations x_1, \dots, x_n are assumed to be generated in two stages. Firstly, the parameters are sampled from the space Ω following a prior distribution G_0 . This prior allows us to incorporate our observations, experiences, knowledge, and so forth, to shape our expectations regarding the model parameters. For instance, in cases where both the transmitter and receiver are situated in the corridor, our prior knowledge suggests that dominant signals are likely to originate from the transmitter's direction. This valuable information can be

mathematically expressed and incorporated into the prior distribution. Secondly, the data is independently sampled from the distribution P_Θ . That is,

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta &\sim G_0 \\ x_1, \dots, x_n | \Theta &\sim_{iid} P_\Theta. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The goal is to estimate the values of the elements of Θ from the observations, which is provided through inferring the posterior distribution $G(\Theta) \triangleq P[\Theta | x_1, \dots, x_n]$ from which the most likely values of the elements of Θ are extracted. Using Bayes' rule, we have

$$G(\Theta \in \Omega) = \frac{\prod_{i=1}^n p(x_i | \Theta) G_0(\Theta)}{\int_{d \in \Omega} \prod_{i=1}^n p(x_i | d) G_0(d) d\Theta}. \quad (2)$$

In almost all scenarios, the explicit expression of the posterior is difficult to provide analytically, if not impossible. Nonetheless, to obtain the posterior and the values of the elements of Θ , there are inference approaches that can be used, such as Gibbs-sampling [12], [13], [15].

An inference model is said to be parametric if the space of the parameters Ω has a finite dimension K that is known a priori. Obviously, this model is not suitable for our case since the number of parameters is unknown. In this case, Ω has to be initially assumed to have infinite dimensions, making the inference model nonparametric, which is the focus of this paper.

B. Inference model

We aim to accurately quantify the AoAs for rays exhibiting strong received power at each location. A ray is said to be *gamma*-optimal if its received power is within γ dB from the maximum received power γ_{Max} (the power of the dominant ray at the same location). In other words, for each measurement point (location), we extract the dominant ray's AoA and its received power γ_{Max} and then all the AoAs with powers that are within γ dB from γ_{Max} , i.e., γ -optimal rays. The outputs of such a data filtering step are the set of AoAs of γ -optimal rays. We also keep track of the locations as we draw statistics on the AoAs coherence distance.

Two types of data representations (outputs) are anticipated

- The PDF of AoAs: in this case, the input is the AoAs of γ -optimal rays. The output is anticipated to be a mixture of wrapped normal distributions.
- The probability of AoAs' correlation as a function of the crossed distance: to elaborate, consider the AoAs γ -optimal rays at two locations, separated by a distance d . The radiation patterns (AoAs) at the two locations are considered β -correlated ($\beta \in [0, 1]$) if their normalized correlation is at least β . We create a binary sequence from the data in which elements take the value '1' if the measurements at two positions exhibit β -correlation. The data is then fed to the learning algorithm to characterize the variation of the AoAs β -correlation probability as a function of the crossed distance.

We divide the measurements into two sets: the first consists of 70% of the total measurements and is exploited to train the statistical model, whereas the remaining measurements are used for validation. Out of the 30% of data, we build a statistical model, which is compared to the learned model (generated out of the 70% of data) using the Kullback–Leibler divergence [20]². The divergence between two distributions, with probability density functions P and Q , can be written as

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P||Q) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(x) \log \left(\frac{Q(x)}{P(x)} \right).$$

Defining the prior distribution $G_0(\theta)$ correctly is of utmost importance, as it encapsulates prior information, including experiences and observations. Two significant challenges must be addressed in this regard. Firstly, it is crucial to select appropriate priors, as arbitrary choices can significantly impact the final distribution. Secondly, during the inference process, we must furnish a closed-form expression for $p(x_i)$ based on the prior $G_0(\theta)$, specifically,

$$p(x_i|G_0) = \int_{\theta \in \Omega} p(x_i|\theta) G_0(\theta) d\theta, \quad (3)$$

for each of the measurement points x_i . Therefore, we are also interested in choosing the prior distribution such that the integral in (3) is tractable. We have considered the histogram $\{x_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ as a prior on the distribution of the means and variances. Since the means and the covariance matrices are independent, $G_0(\theta)$ is simply the product of their individual prior distributions.

We adopt in this paper an algorithm based on MacEachern's Gibbs sampling algorithm, which offers faster convergence compared to the naive Gibbs sampling algorithm [12]. In MacEachern's algorithm, two steps are executed iteratively: associating the measurements to one of the existing clusters (distribution in the mixture) or generating a new one and updating the parameters of each cluster, i.e., the mean m_k and the variance V_k . MacEachern's algorithm gives results for a given process precision α . Mathematical expressions

²The Kullback–Leibler divergence is used to characterize the statistical distance between two distributions. It gives one value and corresponds broadly to the probability of similarity between two distributions.

bind the model precision (the mean squared error between the measurement and the model), α and the size of the data set N [12]. The proposed algorithm outline is described in Algorithm 1. In the algorithm, N_{iter} and ϕ^{-i} denote the number of iterations and the vector that contains the elements of ϕ except for the one associated to ϕ_i .

Algorithm 1: Proposed Algorithm Outline

Initialization:

$\alpha, N_{iter};$

MacEachern Algorithm:

for $L = 1 \rightarrow N_{iter}$ **do**

for $i = 1 \rightarrow N$ **do**

$$P[\phi_i|\phi^{-i}, x_i] = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha}{N+\alpha} \int_{\phi_i \in \Omega_{\theta}} P[x_i|\phi_i] G_0(\phi_i) d\phi_i, & \phi_i \leftarrow \theta_{new} \\ \frac{\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N \delta_{\theta_k}(\phi_j)}{N+\alpha} P[x_i|\theta_k] \forall \theta_k \in \theta, & \phi_i \leftarrow \theta_k \end{cases}$$

$\phi_i \leftarrow \arg \max_{\phi_i \in \Omega_{\theta}} P[\phi_i|\phi^{-i}, \theta, \pi, x_i]$

if $Boolean(\phi_i \leftarrow \theta_{new}) == True$ **then**

$K \leftarrow K + 1$

$\theta \leftarrow \{\theta, \theta_{new}\}$

for $k = 1 \rightarrow K$ **do**

 Update the parameter of k th cluster: (m_k, V_k)

In the above, we briefly discuss the necessary ingredients for the proper functions of the algorithm. A detailed description of the adopted approach and how to apply it can be found in our recent work [21] and in [12], [15].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

It is absolutely certain that the Angle of Arrivals (AoAs) within the channel coherence distance/time are highly correlated. However, the mmWave channel coherence time is only a few microseconds, and thus the coherence distance is only a few millimeters. Note that the channel coherence distance/time and space are interconnected. For instance, the channel coherence time is the duration taken by a mobile device or an obstacle with speed v to cross the channel coherence distance. Therefore, information about one of these parameters provides accurate insights about the other. It is to note that the time intervals between measurement points are in the order of minutes, which means that it extends beyond the channel coherence time. To study the system, we analyze the Probability Density Function (PDF) of AoAs in the measurement environment and the probability of AoAs correlation based on the distance crossed. The latter refers to the correlation between the AoAs at one location and those at another location.

A. On the PDF of AoAs

In this section, we analyze whether or not the AoAs pertaining to the γ -optimal rays (rays within a gap of at most γ dB from the maximum received power at a given location) follow a uniform distribution in an office environment with high NLoS probability. Recall that the sub-6GHz multi-path channel model suggests that AoAs are uniformly distributed, meanwhile, in the case of LoS and two-rays model, AoAs

Fig. 3: AoAs mixture distribution.

Fig. 4: β -correlation probability as a function of the crossed distance.

follow a wrapped Gaussian centered around the direction of the transmitter as claimed in [6]. We investigate the similarity between γ -optimal rays across all the measurement points. Figs. 3a and 3b show that the AoAs follow a mixture of wrapped normal distributions for both cases, namely, for $\gamma = 3\text{dB}$ and $\gamma = 5\text{dB}$ (In each of the figures, we compare the obtained distribution from training measurements to that drawn from the validation measurements.) To start with, it becomes clear that the AoAs are not uniformly distributed, but rather, some directions are much more probable than others. The results support to a certain extent the assumption made in [6] with the exception that we obtained a mixture of distribution instead of a uni-modal distribution. Although it is not straightforward to match the most probable AoAs with the physical architecture due to the obstacle randomness and the dynamics of the environment, we observe that one of the highly probable AoAs revolves around the physical direction of the office doors. It is to be noted that the adopted inference technique gave a reasonable accuracy of more the 95% in the sense of Kullback–Leibler divergence between the distribution

generated through the training data and the one pertaining to the validation data.

Both figures show that the AoAs pertaining to dominant rays follow a mixture of distributions. However, the figures reveal different distributions' variances. This stems from the fact the probability of having 3dB-optimal rays vanishes more rapidly while going away from the direction of the dominant ray. In other words, the 5dB-optimal rays follow a richer scatter channel model.

B. On the space correlation of the AoAs

We analyze the probability of having β -correlation (defined in Sec.III) as a function of the crossed distance, i.e., the probability of having at least β -correlation between the beam patterns of two neighbor measurement points. We consider two values of $\beta = \{80\%, 70\%\}$ where the results are respectively depicted in Figs. 4a and 4b. In contrast to the channel coherence space, which spans approximately half a wavelength and ensures high correlation with a probability one, the AoAs (beam) coherence distance (i.e., beam-steering

coherence space) can extend to the scale of meters, surpassing the channel coherence space, i.e., AoAs do not vary independently from one channel coherence to another. However, the correlation/similarity among AoAs (beam patterns) of neighbor users is probabilistic in nature. For instance, the probability is approximately 0.4 for $\beta = 80\%$ and 0.5 for $\beta = 70\%$ at one foot (30 cm) distance (Recall that the spacing between two successive measurement points is approximately 1 foot.) Moreover, it decays with the distance between users and the correlation level β . Thus, relying solely on the AoAs (beam patterns) of users in the vicinity may not be a reliable strategy for predicting information about a user's AoAs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have carried out a real-world experiment in an effort to support or refute the conjecture of AoAs correlations beyond the channel coherence distance in an environment with high NLoS probability. In fact, it has been the base of some recent works without solid support, where often simulations (typically ray tracing simulator) are used for the analysis and LoS case scenario is considered. The results found in this work are twofold:

- 1) The AoAs of dominant rays are not uniformly distributed but instead are more probable from some direction than others. In particular, AoAs follow a mixture of wrapped normal distributions. The results slightly diverges from the existent work (e.g., two rays model) that has presumed AoAs follow a uni-modal normal distribution.
- 2) The AoAs (beam) coherence distance/time may exceed the channel coherence space/time. However, it is probabilistic in nature. In other words, strong correlation between the beam patterns of neighbor users does not always hold beyond the channel coherence distance. Nevertheless, it does not change randomly from one channel coherence distance to another with considerable probability. For instance, the probability of having at least 70% correlation can reach 1/2 at distance of one foot.

While the experiment substantiates to certain extent the conjecture regarding the non-uniform distribution of AoAs and the beam coherence distance exceeding the channel coherence distance in the indoor office environment, we posit that this concept can be extended to a broader range of environments. This particularly applies to environments with repetitive architectural structures like street canyons and shopping centers. However, further evidence is needed to establish this space/time correlation in various other environments

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